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Kerala, the Supermodel

Kerala has to its credit several social indices well above other Indian States and even on par with developed countries. The recently announced State Policy for Transgenders in Kerala adds another feather to the State's highly decorated cap. Like in the case of many other initiatives in the past, in this sector too Kerala has become the first State to not only formulate a transgender policy but also put in place an effective mechanism for its implementation.

The State registered another record being ranked number one in child welfare in all India 'Rapid Survey on Children 2013-14'. Kerala's Child Development index stands at 0.958 while the national average is far below at 0.530 only.

Apart from social indicators, the State has set a record of sorts in the tourism sector as well. With the fresh tourism season having begun, the State is all set to tap its full potential yet again. Tourism has always had a pride of place in industry sector. The progressive tourism policies adopted by Kerala Government over past four years has transformed tourism into a prominent driver of Kerala's inclusive development.

Kerala tourism won the prestigious Ulysses Award, the highest felicitation awarded by World Tourism Organization which is the tourism wing of UN. Kerala is the first State in India to bag the award for its People's Tourism Project implemented at the International tourist destination of Kumarakom. Inspired by the honour, Kerala tourism has embarked on the 'God's Own Country; People's Own Tourism' project, an encouraging venture to realize the development aspirations of rural Kerala. The National Geographic Travel has identified Kerala as one of the 50 must see destinations in one's life time.

The project 'Visit Kerala', has been recognized globally for its appeal. The State has emerged as a global destination positioning itself as God's own country in World Tourism Map. It is a matter of pride that Tourism department is leaving no stone unturned to promote tourism by contributing to economic, social, political and cultural development of the State.

Mini Antony IAS
Editor in chief

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Improving Civic Services

An Opportunity for the Local Governments in Kerala

While the issues on the quality of civic services have been mounting in the State of Kerala, the XIVth Finance Commission (FFC) has created enormous opportunity for responsive local governments at the cutting edge institutional level of the Grama Panchayats (GPs) and Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) for tackling the same.

The FFC has worked out total grant to the tune of Rs 200, 292.20 Crores to the GPs and Rs 87143.80 Crores to

the ULBs in the country for the period 2015-2020. (FFC Report). These grants are recommended in two parts - Basic Grants and Performance Grants. In the case of Grama Panchayats, 90% of Grants would be Basic Grants and 10% would be Performance Grants. In the case of ULBs, these are respectively 80% and 20%. The purpose of the basic grant is to provide a measure of unconditional support to the Grama Panchayats and ULBs for delivering

the basic functions assigned to them under their respective statutes. The grant provided is intended to be used to improve the status of basic civic services including; water supply, sanitation including septage management, sewerage and solid waste management, storm water drainage, maintenance of community assets, maintenance of roads, footpaths and street-lighting, and burial and cremation grounds.

Need for LGDP

One of the basic

As per the States' share of grants set out by the FFC, the GPs in Kerala State avail Rs 4,017.61 Crores for the period 2015-2020; comprising of Rs 3,615.85 Crores as Basic Grants and Rs 401.76 Crores as Performance Grants. The same for ULBs is to the tune of Rs 3,664.35 Crores; comprising 2,931.48 Crores as Basic Grants and Rs 732.87 Crores as Performance Grants. Thus average FFC grant per GP would be Rs 4.27 Crores and per ULB would be Rs 39.40 Crores for the period 2015-2020. The State has vast experience in participatory planning, since ninth

on planning caution the LSGIs to provide priorities to the components of human development, there are signs of decline in the basic services now envisaged by FFC.

Task of New Team

The new team of Elected Representatives of Local Governments have assumed power. One of the tasks that they have to shoulder is to steer process of preparing LGDP for the forthcoming year, with focus on civic services envisaged by the FFC. The issues on drinking water, waste management, sanitation, connectivity, etc. are mounting alarmingly in Kerala. The State is now facing

The new team of Elected Representatives of Local Governments have assumed power. One of the tasks that they have to shoulder is to steer process of preparing LGDP for the forthcoming year, with focus on civic services envisaged by the FFC.

prerequisites for management of funds of this scale would be to have a cogent development plan at the Local Government level. As per the Constitutional mandate, this plan has to be a participatory plan involving the community, particularly the Grama Sabha (Village Assembly), in the formulation of priorities and projects and will also have to ensure social justice and local economic development mentioned in Article 243G. Therefore the Local Government Development Plan (LGDP) have to be prepared, addressing vulnerabilities of poor and marginalized people by focusing the civic services.

Kerala Context

Kerala State, being played the lead role in decentralization, has to revisit the well established participatory planning methodology so as to tap the enormous opportunity thrown up by the FFC and also to effectively address the mounting problems on civic services in the State.

Five Year Plan (FYP) through Janakeeyasoothranam (Peoples' Plan Campaign) that forms as strength for Kerala to tap this ample opportunity thrown up by FFC and to converge with other sources of funding.

The Participatory Planning Methodology applied during 9th FYP has been continued in the subsequent plans too, with some minor corrections. The Local Self Government Institutions (LSGIs) of Kerala are now in the implementation stage of the fourth annual plan under the 12th Five Year Plan (FYP) during 2012-2017. The State has attempted to simplify the participatory planning procedure during 12th FYP and also to issue the guidelines on time to ensure timely completion of plans and their effective implementation. However a review by KILA on the participatory planning process in the Local Governments revealed that the vibrancy of participatory planning mechanism is declining. Even though the existing guidelines

the threat of new forms of diseases, especially vector-borne diseases. Despite its achievements in terms of educational advancement, the marginalized communities like SC, ST, and traditional Fishermen remain outliers from the arena of higher studies. The educational unemployment and sustainable livelihood of traditional communities are also under threat. All these form as a setback to the well appreciated Kerala Model of Development that the State was acclaimed due to its achievements in health, education, and livelihood. The LSGIs play a significant role in addressing these issues by ensuring the delivery of basic services. Hence the task of new team of Elected Representatives shall be to revisit the participatory planning in Kerala, strengthen the process, and to provide special attention for preparing LGDP with focus on improving the civic services. ■

The writer is Assistant Professor (Planning Management & Development). KILA

DEVELOPMENT

V S SIVAKUMAR
Minister for Devaswom

Development @ Sabarimala

Mandala season has begun. The State Government and Travancore Devaswom Board are giving utmost importance for putting in place facilities for the pilgrims coming in lakhs to the temple to have Darshanam. The present Government has granted huge funds for improving the basic infrastructure facilities at the Sabarimala . A sum of Rs 65 Cr was sanctioned towards the master plan which is being implemented by Devaswom department. Besides, the government has allocated Rs 10 Cr for zero waste project to make Sabarimala waste free. This amount is besides the crores of rupees being spent for the pilgrims by different Departments and Agencies.

The drinking water shortage has been solved by constructing two water reservoirs with a capacity of 20 lakh litres each.

61.27 Cr master plan projects

A number of mega projects became a reality this year at Sabarimala. These include Rs 61, 27 Cr master plan project that has been inaugurated and a waste disposal plant was setup at a cost of 22.87 Cr at Sannidhanam to make the holy Sabarimala garbage free. It is a mega plant with a capacity of 5 MLD. Three incinerators are already functioning for treating solid waste and each have a capacity of treating 700 kg waste in an hour.

Two similar incinerators have been installed at Cheriyavattam in Pampa. A 400 kg incinerator has been set up in Nilackkal. Plastic waste is being collected at Pampa and taken to recycling plant.

Effective disposal of biodegradable

and solid waste have become a reality to a great extent through these waste projects.

The Queue Complexes

Six queue complexes have been constructed this year for devotees who have to stand in queues for Darshanam from Marakootam to Sarankuthi area. This is apart from the two queue complexes constructed here in the previous years. Apart from basic facilities, food is also available at these queue complexes.

The drinking water shortage has been solved by constructing two water reservoirs with a capacity of 20 lakh litres each. Now 1,76,00,000 litre of water can be stored at Sannidhanam. Ahead of last season a parallel pipeline

was constructed from Pampa to Sannidhanam at a cost of 6 Cr. This year toilet blocks have been constructed near Malikappuram and Pampa at the cost of Rs 2.05 Cr and Rs 1.87 Cr respectively. Aerial benched cable was laid for electrification at Sannidhanam at a cost of Rs 4.35 cr, and the work is over.

In Pampa Rs 1.45 Cr spent for storage plant for keeping jaggery and materials for nivediam and other prasadams. A restaurant block and Annadhanam block have been constructed at a cost of Rs 3.78 Cr.

At Nilackal, 14 meter wide roads with foot paths, interlock tiles laid parking yards and 8 metre wide roads have been constructed to link the two areas. The project has cost Rs 8.14 cr.

Water reservoir with a storage

capacity of 10 lakh litres and two bore wells have been installed. Elaborate parking has been arranged with facilities for 10,000 vehicles at a time.

Plans are afoot to implement new project worth Rs 35Cr next year. A new Theerthadana mandapam at the cost of Rs 8 Cr is being constructed at Malikappuram , a 50 room guest house at Pampa and waste management plant etc are part of this mega project.

This Government after coming to power has set aside money for Sabarimala development in every annual budget. Master plan projects are being implemented with the help of Government funds.

Realisation of long term aspirations

The Government is giving top priority for fulfilling the long

term aspirations of devotees. A Nadapanthal has been constructed from Pampa to Marakkootam on the Kanana patha. Swami Ayyappan road and Chandranadhan road have been linked up through underpass along the Pampa-Sannidhanam route at Marakkootam. Swami Ayyappan road is now open for tractor traffic. Cables have been laid to ensure smooth electrification and to avoid accidents in these areas.

Water supply has been expanded and toilet facilities have been put in place at many places. Resting areas have been earmarked. Donkeys are being avoided to carry goods from Pampa to Sannidhanam. Through this step we have been able to check maltreatment of animals and also provide jaggery without any contamination.

Modern medicine, Ayurveda , Homeopathy medical facilities are all available under one roof.

Pampa Manappuram has been cleaned up and beautified with tiles. Service roads from Pampa Triveni to Ganapathy temple have been constructed with the help of Ayyappa Seva Sanghom. The pathways near Pampa temple have been widened to control the crowds at Pampa

Arogya Bhavan

Arogya Bhavan in Pampa is the mile stone of Sabarimala development project. Modern medicine, Ayurveda , Homeopathy medical facilities are all available under one roof. This is the first of its kind in the State. Casualty services, cardiology critical care unit, operation theatre, laboratory, pharmacy and facilities have been provided at this centre. As many as 30 persons can be treated as in patients at a time. Staff quarters have been constructed for doctors and paramedical staff. Health department's hospital complex is being constructed at a cost of Rs 5.5 cr.

A 10,210 sq feet two story building is coming up at Sannidhanam.

During the last four and half years Rs 523 cr has been spent for the renovation of Sabarimala Road. For the current season Rs 95.5 Cr has been allocated to six districts.

Besides, Rs 76.55 Cr project has been given approval for modernising the roads with three year guarantee. This include Kottayam, Pathanamthitta districts and 11 roads in connection with Sabarimala. Pampa- Chalakayam road has been modernised using the BMC technology. A bridge has been constructed at Kanamala at Rs 7 Cr –to make Erumeli –Pampa journey comfortable.

It is the responsibility of each devotee to protect the holiness of Sabarimala and Punyapookavanam situated in the midst of forest. The collective efforts of all devotees are required. I seek the cooperation of all devotees and all other connected, for the success of Mandala Makaravilakku festival. ■

COVER STORY

■ A P ANILKUMAR
Minister for Tourism

THE PROMISED LAND

In the mornings, from nearly anywhere in Kerala, you can hear loud music from the Hindu temples, wailing muezzins at the mosques, and church bells ringing at the cathedrals. Religious tolerance is just one reason for Kerala's success. The state government has effected sweeping land reforms and spends almost half of its budget on health and education. A heritage of female headed households means women have always been equal participants here.

"This small state in India, though not much larger than Maryland, has a population as big as California's. But its infant mortality rate is low, its literacy rate is among the highest on Earth, and its birth rate is below America's and falling faster. Kerala's citizens live nearly as long as Americans or Europeans. Though mostly a land of paddy-covered plains, statistically Kerala stands out as Mount Everest of social development; there's truly no place like it."

Concerted efforts and well-conceived ideas have made Kerala the promised land of the globe-trotter.

Thus remarks Bill McKibben, travelogue writer for The National Geographic Traveller, on Kerala. It is this unique social environment and unparalleled geographic bounty that earned Kerala the motif “God’s Own Country”. A strip of a State on the South-Western edge of Indian Peninsula, Kerala is just 650km long and 120km at its widest, sandwiched between the Arabian Sea towards the West and a tropical mountain range widely known as Western Ghats in the east. The biosphere has given rise to unique herbs, spices, fruits and animals so rare that their presence altered the history of this land. It was the birthplace of pepper, in an era when pepper was valued more than gold, thus aiding trade and setting up of seaports thereby scripting a distinctive history for the State. Kerala’s unique position in history also imparts a rich cultural heritage and adds flavour to the tourism industry, the State being the most sought after destination worldwide for centuries, right from the days of King Solomon.

Kerala's cultural, aesthetic and social grandeur is so appealing that the tourists' acknowledgement and appreciation of its richness is often more ardent than the natives'.

It is this potent and unique topographic strength that enabled the momentous growth of Kerala's tourism sector even during the period of global recession. The rising number of domestic and foreign tourists visiting Kerala and the consequent rise in income from tourism sector over the past five years bears testimony to this significant achievement. While 9381455 domestic and 732985 foreign tourists visited Kerala in 2011 - 12, the numbers rose to 10076854 and 793696 respectively in 2012 - 13. In the year 2013 -14, Kerala hosted 10857811 domestic and 858143 foreign tourists and in 2014 -15, 11695411 domestic and 923366 foreign tourists respectively. Concurrently, the income rose from 19037crore (including 4221crore as foreign currency) in 2011-12 to 20430crore (4571crore as foreign currency) in 2012-13. While in 2013-14, the state earned 22695crore (5560.77crore as foreign

currency) from tourism, it rose to 24885.44crore (6398.93crore as foreign currency) in 2014-15. The income from tourism constitutes around 10% of Kerala's GDP and is the second largest contributor to the state's GDP after IT sector. The current calendar year has witnessed a 7% increase over the past year's inflow of tourists with 7.75 lakh foreign and 76.71lakh domestic tourists visiting the state over the past ten months and the growth is expected to reach 10% by the end of this financial year.

By substantially expanding the social base of tourism and deconstructing the status of tourism as the exclusive recreation of affluent, the progressive tourism policies adopted by Kerala government over past four years has transformed tourism into a prominent driver of Kerala's inclusive development. It is also worth noting that Kerala has been able to strike a rapport with our neighbour and strong competitor in tourism, Srilanka and also China, with whom exchanges in tourism had been severely constrained following the camaraderie of ancient days,

thus creating a promising platform to engage cooperatively in tourism programs and projects.

The Ulysses in Tourism

Kerala tourism won the prestigious Ulysses Award, the highest felicitation awarded by World Tourism Organization, the tourism wing of UN. Kerala is the first State in India to bag the award for its People's Tourism Project implemented at the International tourist destination of Kumarakom. Inspired by the honour, Kerala tourism has embarked on the 'God's Own Country; People's Own Tourism' project, an encouraging venture to realize the development aspirations of rural Kerala. The mission of the project is to let tourists partake in the pulse of village life in all its essence and thereby channel the benefits of tourism into rural lives. Flagged off in 2014-15, the project was accompanied by the 'Visit Kerala' campaign formulated by the State to spice up the tourists' platter with Kerala's authentic taste by organizing a range of attractive events including festivals, carnivals, arts and sports exhibitions, food

festivals and adventure and water sports. The campaign has been recognized globally for its appeal. It is also a matter of pride that Tourism department features first among the State departments in category three of the State Planning Board's report on sector wise implementation of government schemes for the year 2013-14.

People's Tourism project was conceived as a sequel to Responsible Tourism. The mission of this scheme is to harness the participation of natives in tourism industry through local self-governing institutions and enable tourism entrepreneurs to deliver the fruits of tourism industry to the natives in tourism destinations. The project has won numerous national and international accolades and is the nation's model tourism project.

The State government has framed a holistic tourism policy to ensure the effective implementation of People's Tourism project. Kerala's tourism potential can be realized to the fullest only through productive engagement of private investors. The consistent and significant growth of Kerala tourism even during the period of international recession was an upshot of the favourable tourism policies adopted by the State and the effort of private investors who put faith in the government's policies. In this context, the new tourism policy, in addition to dominant State intervention in tourism industry and protection of the ecosystem and bio diversity, will also entail the expansion of infrastructural amenities to support private investors.

In an unfortunate incident, the sea plane service which was formally

Kerala's tourism potential can be realized to the fullest only through productive engagement of private investors.

inaugurated in Kerala had to be stalled due to concerns raised by certain sections of the fishermen community. In accordance with recommendations of the report submitted by the expert committee appointed by the State to study the issue, changes have been suggested in the location of water dromes associated with the sea plane. The project which is expected to be a huge incentive to Kerala's tourism is all set to recommence its service from September after making the proposed alterations.

The objective of the government is to utilize opportunities dynamically. A Parliamentary Subcommittee to

design opportune projects and see through their time bound approval and implementation has been set up. A State level Advisory Committee to ensure the partnership of private investors and a Tourism Investment Board to foster and strengthen the investor friendly environment has also been constituted. Kerala is also a forerunner in the expansion of basic tourist amenities. According to the survey conducted by Kerala state tourism department, the number of hotels and resorts adjoining tourism destinations has doubled from 3000 in the year 2011 to 6000 presently. Similar growth has been recorded in the number of tour operators as well.

Over the past four years, the State Tourism has been able to completely utilize allocated funds and also transition into the implementation phase of majority of approved projects.

Effective utilisation of IT

Kerala has been a pioneer in the effective utilisation of the advances in information technology for the promotion of its tourism. A model for the nation in this arena, Kerala has been a consistent winner of the award constituted by Centre for the same. Through operative employment of technology in tourism promotion, the state has been able to significantly reduce expenses in this area. Kerala's prime position in number of Google searches is also indicative of its skillful use of information technology with Kerala tourism's official website currently accessible in 11 foreign and 10 Indian languages, expanding the boundaries of God's Own Country beyond the barriers of language.

With over 42 lakh visitors over the past year, this website has won the Centre's "Webratna" award for responsible e-governance.

Along with innovative tourism products the State Government has also indulged in creative promotional strategies. Promotional activities presenting Kerala as the abode of Ayurvedic heritage on the international arena and featuring the picturesque bio diversity of Western Ghats and gentle backwaters of rural hinterlands were highly fruitful. The transition from seasonal to all season tourism by providing attractive discounts during off season proved to be a further impetus. Also, the promotional activities expanded beyond our usual foreign markets to Sri Lanka, China, Russia, Australia and Middle East, furthering the enterprise of Kerala's tourism industry.

Visa on Arrival

"Visa on Arrival" was a novel

scheme that necessitated tourists from Japan, Myanmar, Malaysia, Singapore and other 43 countries to obtain visa only after arriving at the destination. With the Trivandrum and Cochin international airports offering this facility, Kerala becomes the only State to have two airports under the ambit of this scheme. A huge incentive to tourists, actions are underway to make this facility available to tourists from more countries and thus attract more visitors to our state. The Government is also planning to revamp the promotion of "Visa on Arrival" scheme.

In order to accommodate the increasing number of tourists visiting the State, Kerala Government has framed master plans for basic facilities to be implemented in the international tourism centers mainly Kovalam, Kumarakom, Thekkady, Fort Kochi and Munnar with a time frame spanning the next 30 years and

intents to begin the execution during the current financial year itself. In addition, the master plans for Nila Heritage Tourism for promotion of tourism in the Malabar region, Golden Valley Tourism Circuit centered on Ponmudi, Ashtamudi Tourism Plan centered on Kollam, Kaladi-Malayatoor Tourism Circuit and Nilamboor Tourism projects are

by the State Tourism Department.

Numerous mega tourism projects that could strengthen Kerala's development process including the Spice Route Tourism Project, Muziris Heritage Tourism Project, Alappuzha Backwaters Megatourism Project, Thallaserry Heritage Tourism Project and Kochi Tourism Project are progressing. The Government is zealously engaged in efforts to harness funds for tourism projects from the Centre. Over the years 2011-14, the Centre has allocated

awards in addition to the Ulysses award, including the Best Green Destination award and the Best Family Destination award.

While the previous ministry spent 507 crore over five years on both small and big tourism projects, the present ministry has already spent over 660 crore over the past four years on 353 projects. It is worth noting that the present Government placed more emphasis on the development of basic infrastructure and amenities.

Along with projects, the State lays

The Clean Kerala campaign to maintain the tourism spots clean and waste free is also being effectively undertaken by the State Tourism Department.

ongoing.

Steps to implement the most advanced tourism signage system to provide tourists visiting the state with travel related information, most importantly travel directions, are progressing. The QR code embedded in signboards could be scanned using smartphones to gauge information on tourism centers and basic amenities in the vicinity and also visit the tourism website. The Clean Kerala campaign to maintain the tourism spots clean and waste free is also being effectively undertaken

83.86crore for tourism projects comprising Thamboormuzhy, Drum Fest, expansion of the tourism cruise berthing facility in Kochi, Alappuzha Mega Project, Kappil Beach – Boat Club development, Palaikkari Fish Farm Tourism expansion and development of Bhoothathankettu tourist destination. Over this period, Kerala tourism has won more than two dozen national and international

due emphasis on the development of human resource capabilities in the tourism sector. Government enterprises in tourism sector such as KITTS, KTDC and Foodcraft Institutes offer diverse vocational courses. The vocational courses offered by the Foodcrafts Institutes in association with Kudumbashree to the children of Kudumbashree members, has resulted in the creation of numerous job opportunities among ordinary citizens. KTDC's vocational training program in hospitality sector for SC youth with guaranteed employment in Gulf countries has been quite successful in implementation.

KTDC, the government enterprise in tourism sector, crossed a historical 100crore mark in income during 2012-13. It earned 105crore as savings in 2013-14 which crossed over to a whopping 138crore with a 33% increase in income during 2014-15, setting an all-time record. It is also worth noting that KTDC,

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Sustainable Tourism

Following sustainability norms in tourism is a responsible approach. Sustainable Tourism is a model of economic development that exemplifies stewardship of environment and sensitivity to community and cultural aspiration. It seriously considers the conservation and preservation of the physical

and cultural environment of a region. Sustainable Tourism will not degrade the natural resources of the destination and traditional livelihood of a community..

Sustainability is essential in the tourism industry as it involves manpower, tourist attractions, infrastructure, service know how, financial resources, and business management. It also has a bearing on the environment, society, ecology, and legal environment.

Tourism being a mega industry, larger planning and management is essential to control the industry and to preserve environment. When dealing with such serious issues, sustainable tourism concept comes handy and helpful. It is all about conserving resources, valuing the local culture and tradition and contributing largely in economy. Sustainable Tourism is 'Responsible Tourism', intending to generate employment and income along with minimizing impact on environment and local culture.

Kerala has adopted the Responsible Tourism model that encourages the

Sustainable Tourism will not degrade the natural resources of the destination and traditional livelihood of a community.

traditional activities of the local community and remunerates them for their contribution and participation in the tourism industry. Selected locations in Kerala like Kovalam, Kumarakom, Thekkady, and Kumbalangi have adopted the Responsible Tourism practice where tourists are taken to experience the local life creating an income opportunity for the locals. Also, the hotels buy back the local produces from the local community instead of procuring it from the general market. The community practices organic cultivation and pollution free environment.

In sustainable tourism it gives importance to the local culture and tradition. Sustainable Tourism is informatory as well. The tourists are informed well about the destinations, its community, the

specialty of the culture, and the civilization. Vice-versa the local community will know the culture and practices of the visiting tourists. It envisages deeper involvement of locals and also it stresses upon the integrity of tourism locations.

There are some principles to be followed for sustainability in tourism. With the increased footfall of tourists, there is a higher need that arises to plan and manage the industry suitably. It should follow guidelines, principles, codes, ethics and fair guidelines. Training and education have to be provided to heighten importance of heritage and natural resources.

Kerala tourism follows sustainable tourism model adopting various suitable parameters. Kerala believes in qualitative tourism attracting limited number of visitors who are high spenders and who value local culture, community and

environment. The State has evolved a good model of Private Public Partnership in the tourism industry so that quality management is ensured. It also adheres to Environmental Impact norms, Coastal Regulatory Zone norms and others. It also insists on promotion of Eco practices.

Eco tourism is a major vertical in sustainable tourism. While Eco tourism deals with nature based tourism focusing on conserving the environment and improving well-being of local people, Sustainable Tourism includes all segments of tourism including Health Tourism which has recently become the major thrust area of tourism development in Kerala. We need to recognize the strengths of Health Tourism for a Sustainable Tourism industry. Health tourism should ensure economic progress, and environmental preservation. It will contribute to the sustainable development through their entire service chain. All service providers and stakeholders of Medical Tourism have to follow the principles of environmental,

Health tourism should ensure economic progress, and environmental preservation.

economic and social sustainability.

Kerala is identified as the most ideal location for Medical treatment and recuperative leisure. The State is known for its alternative medical therapies such as Ayurveda. There are sophisticated medical hospitals of International standards in Kerala. There is no hassle of waiting time for treatments and procedures. There are specialized doctors in almost all major disciplines. The people of Kerala are known as hospitable and compassionate. There is an eco-friendly environment in the State. Majority of the population in Kerala are conversant in the global language English. There is ample opportunity for investments in hospitals, R&D facility, medical device manufacturing facility etc.

With all these favorable features Kerala has come a long way in the development of tourism. Now it is time to embark on an aggressive infrastructure buildup and marketing joining hands together by the private sector and the Government to make Kerala a 'God's Own Country' in its true sense. ■

The writer is Managing Director, Air Travel Enterprises India Ltd., Thiruvananthapuram

Winding Ways to Great Adventures

Wayanad, the northern most hill district of Kerala, with its mist clad mountains, spice plantations, terraced tea gardens, coffee estates and jungles is a breathtakingly beautiful place.

Though very small in size, Wayanad offers an array of tourism experience for a discerning traveller.

From the jungles of Muthanga and tholpetty, to the cliffs of chembra peak, the

nature trails are amazing.

For a nature traveller Wayanad is a beehive of activities from, treks, jungle safari, bamboo rafting, birding, and walks through the country side and more!

For a sightseeing tourist, the attractions include the pristine

Pookot lake, for the whole family to enjoy, the hills of Banasura form the majestic backdrop of the Banasura Dam where one can do speed boating. For a photographer this place offers amazing landscape, Banasura also is a great place for birding

enthusiasts.

The edakkal caves takes you through the ages of civilisation .Kuruvadeep islands near Mananthavady not only is the catchment area for cauvery,but, the womb of river Kabini ,one of the 3 sacred east flowing rivers of Kerala.

The treks through the uninhabited islands are mesmerising and is a birding paradise.

The southern part of Wayand harbours the big mountain ranges like Chembra and Vellarimala. These are stunning biodiversity spots with scenic valleys and sholas forests.

These are the birth place of many rivulets and streams that supply

to behold ,with misty sprays during the monsoon and right water levels even in summer.

The DTPC/Kerala Tourism conducts through RT cell various village life experiences inside the district, that showcases various nuances of the ways of Wayand, besides helping local communities.

The Karalad lake is a newest adventure destination of Wayand, where one can do zip line ,river crossing ,zorbng, besides staying in eco friendly tents ,with all modern amenities. The zip line is one of the longest in kerala. There are canoes for more adventurous to enjoy the lake ,this besides a family can enjoy the regular paddle and row boats.

There are newer things on the anvil at this

newer adventure tourism options the district can do.

Priyadarshini Te a Environs, can rightly be called as a destination in itself with all that is required by a discerning traveller. To start with this has 7 rooms in old bungalow, with typical kerala cusine to pamper your palate. There are more cottages, that will be added. The sheer natural beauty of this place under the banasura hills ,is so enchanting. A tourist can devote,a day for going through the tea estates,see transformation of greentea leaves from the garden to how is packeted into commercial tea. The entire set up is run by the local Tribal community ,and you not only enjoy your holiday, but, also contribute to a cause.

There are small creeks, ponds, waterfalls that add to the general aura of the place, making

endless water to the district and feed some mighty rivers elsewhere like chaliyar. The lofty ranges also harbours endemic bird and plant species. The meenmutty,Soochipara and Kanthampara water falls are sight

adventure zone. There are going to be rappelling stimulators, for high adrenaline youth, skating rink ,cycling track etc. The DTPC has added glory to natural beauty of the lake by opening up

Priyadarshini Tea Environs a destination within destination!

What else do a traveller needs from jungles, to great climate to hills, and experiences! all in 1 Destination -Wayanad. ■

The writer is Sub Collector and Member Secretary, DTPC, Wayanad

A Qualitative Approach to Tourism

The Kerala Model

Tourism development in Kerala reveals that the covetable achievement of the State in this sector is mainly attributed to the concerted efforts taken in product development, marketing, skill and capacity building and sustainable development.

Product Development

Kerala has carved a niche in product development focusing its natural and cultural endowments. The tourism commodity basket of Kerala includes beaches, backwaters, hill stations scenic spots, wildlife, adventure sports, ayurveda, fairs, festivals, performing arts, heritage sites, medical

life. Product development focusing on natural and cultural attractions has resulted in attracting special interest tourist particularly for experiencing Beach tourism, Backwater tourism, Eco tourism, Wellness tourism, Adventure tourism, Pilgrim tourism, Cultural tourism, Heritage tourism, Rural tourism, Hill tourism, Festival tourism and Medical value tourism. Concurrently, efforts are also taken for value addition to these attractions by providing facilities for water sports, different types of house boats in back waters, tree houses, tented accommodation, home stays, ethnic restaurant, wellness therapy, facilitation centers, village life experience packages, performing arts, adventure sports and other cultural programmes on demand etc. They enable the tourist to derive rich and authentic experiences from the core attractions resulting in ensuring value for money.

House boats are awarded Gold star or Silver star certification depending on the optional condition they satisfy in addition to the essential conditions which all of them have to meet. In the accommodation sector besides classified hotels, facilities are provided by Home stays and Serviced villas which operate in a family environment. To ensure quality certification is introduced after classifying them based on the quality of facilities and services offered. Home stays are classified as Diamond House, Gold house and Silver house. The latest in setting quality standards is the Responsible Tourism classification to accommodation units in destinations.

Based on Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria, Kerala has developed separate standards for evaluating the management, economic, social and environmental aspects pertaining to the operation of accommodation units. The Responsible Tourism classified accommodation units are committed to ensure sustainable operations giving due weightage to social, economic environmental and management responsibility. The philosophy behind this is to make destination better place for tourist to visit and better place for community to live.

Marketing

The volume of sales, by and large, is determined by the marketing strategy. Print, electronic and visual media are widely used by Kerala to reach out both domestic and international customers, keeping in mind the significance of word of mouth publicity. The major source markets for foreign tourist to Kerala are UK, USA, France, Germany, Australia, Malaysia, Canada, Netherland and Maldives. The domestic source markets mainly emanates from within the State followed by Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, marketing Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Delhi.

The active involvement and participation of the Department of tourism and private players have immensely contributed in marketing Kerala across the globe. However, the State firmly believes that round the year tourism business can be sustained only if the state can attract sizable portion of domestic tourist also.

Apart from these national and international trade and road shows steps are being taken by the stake holders in tourism to bring business operators to Kerala as part of marketing initiative. The Kerala Travel Mart conducted once in two years, the Medical value tourism conference organized periodically and the B2B meet of Homestay operators launched in 2015 are other major

Skill and Capacity Development

Tourism, the service industry demand professionalism for its operation. For developing quality human resource in tourism, separate institutional arrangements have been made by the government. The Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel Studies (KITTS) one of the premier institutes in tourism in the State mould professionals by conducting various tourism based courses and training programmes. This ISO certified, AICTE approved institute offers MBA and BBA in tourism affiliated to University of Kerala, Diploma and Certificate programme in Airport Operations, Logistic Management, IATA courses and Guide training programme at State and Local Levels. KITTS also undertake research and consultancy services besides, conducting various training and capacity building programme to stake holders in tourism.

As nodal agency for implementing Responsible Tourism initiative in Kerala, KITTS is extending its services to grass root

levels in all the 14 districts

in the state. Training of youths under Hunar Se Rozgar Tak programme, Skill development to the poor and marginalized drawing support from various Government Departments in tourism and hospitality ensured regular and continuous supply of skilled personels to tourism sector making tourism in Kerala more professional business. ■

The writer is Principal, KITTS, Thiruvananthapuram

initiatives taken within the State for bringing customers and business operators to Kerala as part of marketing.

The increased acceptance of marketing using electronic gadgets is evidenced in the increased number of users of Departments websites and online reservations. The persistent efforts taken in marketing not only helped to maintain existing markets but enabled the state to open new markets also.

Kerala, the God's own country, has many a feather in its cap. Widely hailed as the green paradise and land of spices, Kerala is one among the 13 must see destinations in the world. Of late, Thekkadi, famous for its scenic beauty in Periyar Tiger Reserve has been awarded as the world's top most emerging destinations by Pacific Asia Travel Association in 2015.

Towards Sustainability

The leniency of tourism towards nature based tourism products started in 1990s. This has assumed different forms such as green tourism, rural tourism, responsible tourism, sustainable tourism, pro poor tourism and so on. The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) in its green economy report in

Know the Geography while enjoying it

Geo tourism is gaining momentum in Kerala

2012 opined that, “tourist choices are increasingly influenced by sustainability considerations”. The WTO estimates that, while the overall tourism is growing at the rate of 4 %, the nature based tourism is growing in between 10 % and 30 %.

Geo tourism

Geo tourism primarily aims to enjoy the geographical features of a particular place in its totality. It is a sustainable tourism product, which provides the scope for enjoying unique geographical features of a destination such as natural beauty, aesthetics, landscapes, culture, heritage, pilgrims, festivals, nature of living, cuisine, and sometimes the local people itself. Earlier this tourism product was limited to visiting geo morphological structures, such as mountains, volcanic eruptions, mines, river beds and so on. But now this product is more based, and is intended to enjoy anything lying on a place.

Tourism now becomes a multi-segmented industry with attractive and growing segments, viz., ecotourism, heritage or pilgrim, rural tourism, responsible tourism, MICE tourism, shopping festivals and so on.

Sustainability and Geotourism

The basis of sustainability is the judicious use of resources. It

includes protection and promotion of physical, human and natural resources, flora, and fauna in such a way as to ensure development of all the sections of that locality.

E.g., in Munnar, the top most hill station in South India, the natural serenity alone is not the prime attraction. The curling misty tea gardens, charm of mighty Western Ghats, natural milky streams, waterfalls, Nilgiri thars, kurinji all are matters of attraction. Along with this the blooming winter makes Munnar a visitor’s paradise. The Nilgiri thars at Rajamala, and the soft trekking are adventurous. Top station is caressing and eco point is enthusiastic. Along with this boating at Mattupetty and Kundala dams are refreshing.

The tourism potentialities of Munnar is not yet tapped fully even after having this much of attractions in a limited geographical area. The life styles of the people, cuisine, heritage, culture, adventure, etc., are not given sufficient attraction.

Alleppy is not an exception. Boating alone is not the matter of attraction. Lush green paddy fields below the sea level, overnight stay in house boats, cuisine; Karimeen, Alleppy coir, Nehru Trophy snake boat festival etc do matter.

The same is the case with Thiruvananthapuram, Ernakulam and Wayanad. These have the

potential of developing multiple tourism products in a single destination are not yet explored properly. The birth place of circus in Kerala, Thalasseri is famous for its Dum Biryani. Bakel fort and Chandragiri, and Theyyam in Kasaragode have much to cater to the aesthetic sense of the globe-trotter. Palakkad, Tipu’s fort undoubtedly is an attraction. And, the heritage of Kalpathi is also important.

One typical example were Geotourism is practicing in Kerala is at Thekkadi. That may be the reason why, Thekkadi is awarded as the best emerging destination in the world in 2015 by PATA. Once, boating was the only attraction in Thekkadi. Now ecotourism and related activities become the prime attraction. These ecotourism programs are evolved out as a means of providing alternative livelihood to the poachers and sandal smugglers. This has given birth to the formation of Eco Development Committees, and Periyar Tiger Trial. Now PTT is offering various types of hard core and soft core ecotourism programs – jungle inn, tribal village, jungle patrol, all are well structured, planned and organized. The element of heritage, adventure, life style of tribes, cuisine everything is given considerable attention and are gaining momentum, without acknowledging the name of Geotourism. ■

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COVER STORY

■ SWARAJ M, Dr. S SATHEES CHANDRAN

Film induced tourism in Kerala

Film tourism is growing with very specific market segments based on consumers' interests and values. With more than 600 television channels, 100 million pay-TV households, 70,000 newspapers and 1,000 films produced annually in India, Entertainment (M&E) industry provides attractive growth opportunities globally. Tourists are more experienced and become selective in their choice of holidays and destination activities.

Kerala tourism has reached the point of maturity and marketing the film induced destinations. Tourists need to be attracted to the destinations which have to be promoted effectively to keep up the market share and attract new market segments. Athirappally

waterfall has recently welcomed a few Baahubali movie fans. Baahubali is a costly and greatest Indian box-office movie directed by S.S. Rajamouli. Also Tamil movie Punnagai Mannan was shot near the falls; the falls itself play a role in the Film. It made the falls so popular in Tamil Nadu that it got the nickname Punnagai Mannan Falls. Movies directed by Mani Ratnam - Raavan and Dilse have filmed a romantic number in the Athirapilly waterfalls. Athirappally is the destination internationally accepted by tourist through various English movies such as Before the Rains (2007) Pirate's blood (2008).

The charming beauty of Kerala such as hill stations, forts, heritage buildings,

Show it on screen and Get

IFFK

International Film Festivals of Kerala

Film festivals like the International Film Festival of Kerala (IFFK) and International documentary and short film festival of Kerala (IDSFK) are attracted to mass press, celebrities and film enthusiasts from all over the world

Benefits

Boost to the tourism industry

Boost the local film production

Creation of employment opportunity

Benefits to the economy

Technological exchange

Cultural exchange

waterfall, backwaters, and the lakes have always attracted Indian and foreign filmmakers.

The Kerala Government has invited film industries across India to shoot in the State for promoting the State's pleasing tourist hotspots through movies. Kerala government has launched 'Visit Kerala Campaign' to join hands with the movie industry for the promotion of film tourism. The main film tourism stakeholders such as Kerala State Film Development Corporation Ltd (KSFDC), film productions unit and crews, tourism agencies

and Film Employees Federation of Kerala (FEFKA), and Malayalam Cine Technicians Association (MACTA) of the film industry have offered support in all international and domestic promotional activities carried out by the tourism department.

There have been an increasing number of tourists visiting destinations featured in films and television series which are not directly related to tourism promotion campaigns. This trend is called film-induced tourism or movie-induced tourism. The visitors spend in the same destination as featured in the movie, where they can also enjoy the same.

On-locations

On-locations are film locations in the natural surroundings like real buildings and streets. Some locations have tourist attractiveness of their own and other sites can experience

a high ascend in visitor popularity because of their appearance in a film

Off-location tourism

Off-locations are simulated and built mainly for the filming or for tourism purposes like film studios or film parks. In India, major film studios are Ramoji Rao film city, MGR film city, Noida Film city and Mumbai Film City. Ramoji Rao film city was launched in 1996 in Hyderabad, which is built entirely for operating as either film studio tours or themed film parks.

The Chithranjali Film in Trivandrum studio shows people how the actual filming process happens. These are places that are primarily built for filming and production purposes and secondarily used for tourist tours. ■

The writers are Research Scholar in Management, Kerala University, Director, Gurudev Institute of Management, Kadakkal

it marketed

The State is primarily famed for its panoramic backwaters, tranquil beaches, hill stations and greenery which lure tourists from all parts of the world to the State. Better known as God's own country it was a relatively unknown tourist destination until the early 1960's. Kerala Government strongly realized the importance and potentials of tourism during the mid 1980's. Tourism was recognized as an industry in Kerala during the year 1986 and it was also the

first state to declare it as an industry in the country.

Presence of International Destinations

Since time immemorial Kerala had trade relations with major countries. The European travellers discovered the potentiality of Kovalam as a beach tourism destination during 1930's. Kovalam came into limelight in the early seventies and this started the makeover of a coastal fishing village into one of the most

prime international tourist destinations in the country. Kumarakom is the first and most renowned responsible tourism destination in the country famed for village visits and houseboat cruises through the Vembanad backwaters. Kochi famed for colonial monuments and Alleppey known as the Venice of the East are globally renowned tourism destinations. Other international destinations in the State are Malayattoor, Munnar, Thekkady, Kuttanad etc.

In stock Surprises

Unique selling propositions (USP's)

Backwaters and Houseboats are nicknamed as the mascots of Kerala Tourism. The prominent backwaters are Vembanad and Ashtamudi. Vembanad is known as the hub of backwater tourism while Ashtamudi is known as the gateway to backwaters.

Tree huts and home stays attract hordes of tourist because of its unique designs and novel features. Monsoon is one among the unique selling propositions (USP's) of Kerala tourism and the wellness packages

based on Ayurveda during monsoon are attracting flock of tourist to visit the State. Availability of trained physicians and good facilities for treatments are the features of Kerala Ayurveda. Medical tourism is developing at a fast pace in Kerala because of the presence of world class hospitals, highly skilled doctors and quality treatments offered at very economical rates.

Authentic festivals & season based fairs

Kerala is a State having year round fairs, festivals and folklores

which are always great attractions for the tourist. Some of the notable festivals and fairs are Chettikulangara Kettukazcha, Uthralikavu Pooram, Nenmara Vallengi Vela, Malabar Mahotsavam, Muzhappilangad beach fest, Nattika beach fest; Malabar crafts fair, Cochin carnival etc. The eighth edition of the Kerala Travel Mart KTM-2014 concluded with more than the expected response from all the participants

Grand Kerala Shopping Festival is a forty six day shopping festival organized by the Government

of Kerala in association with Department of Tourism . Kochi-Muziris Biennale is the only event from India mentioned in the 'thirteen cultural events to be seen' listed by Forbes Magazine.

Vibrant Tourism Events

Thrissur Pooram is one of the festival with wide variety of attractions like – melams, vadhyaams, processions, fireworks, colourful illuminations etc. witnessed by mass number of foreign & domestic tourists. Even though Thrissur pooram is a week long festival the most spectacular events of pooram is held during the last thirty six hours which includes Kudamattam (display of colorful umbrellas) and Vedikkettu (fire work displays).

Kerala Tourism has identified several festivals including snake boat races and Ox races as part of promoting its monsoon tourism. Nehru Trophy Boat Race - nicknamed as Kuttanad's Olympics

on Water is an exceptional tourism event. SPLASH carnival held in Wayanad and Malabar river festival are the notable ones.

Innovative Campaigns & Promotions

The innovative measures, strategies and marketing campaigns by the Department of tourism (DoT) & Kerala Tourism Development Corporation (KTDC) through their websites & brochures to promote tourism are of high standards which enable the state to become the trendsetters.

Visit Kerala 2015–Season of Surprises

The initiative started from April 2015 for a period of one year comprises a series of events ranging from arts to sports and the main focus will be to strengthen the promotion of tourism products like Ayurveda, Responsible Tourism, Spice Route and Muziris. Cultural festivals, weddings, Meetings, Incentives,

Conferences and Exhibitions (MICE) and adventure tourism will be promoted aggressively as part of Visit Kerala 2015.

Responsible Strategies & Initiatives

The State is famed especially for its responsible rural tourism and eco-tourism initiatives. The introduction of visa on arrival (VoA) service at Thiruvananthapuram and Kochi airports are allowing citizens from specified countries to obtain tourist visas upon arrival in Kerala. Kerala Tourism launched 'hop-on hop-off' boat services and water taxis during last year to ensure last mile connectivity and explore the tropical coastline and backwaters in and around Kochi effectively.

Promising ongoing and upcoming tourism projects

Kerala Tourism has signed an agreement with UNESCO to begin a historic cooperation in promoting and protecting the

PHOTO: BIJU

ancient spice route heritage. The other notable ongoing project is the Nila Heritage Tourism circuit. The circuit includes a comprehensive tourism resource identification, mapping and documentation of history, art, culture, heritage, traditions, customs

and biodiversity of the Nila River flowing through Thrissur, Palakkad, and Malappuram districts.

One of the major reasons for the success of tourism in the State was due to the practice of ecologically responsible and sustainable tourism

concepts which focuses on the local culture and heritage conservation, wilderness adventures, volunteering and benefits for the host population. ■

The writer is Lecturer, School of Tourism Studies, Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam

Kerala pavilion bags twin gold medals at IITF

India International Trade Fair 2015 conducted at Pragathi Maidan, Delhi ended with a golden note making Kerala first prize winner of two prestigious awards. Kerala bagged gold medals for the best State pavilion and for the best Food Court. I&PRD Director Mini Antony IAS received the awards from Arun Jaitley, Finance Minister, Govt of India .

Framing a new

State Policy for Transgenders in Kerala, 2015 is a landmark policy declaration by the Govt. of Kerala. Kerala is the first State in India to formulate a transgender policy and a mechanism for implementation. The policy document was officially released at the International Conference on Gender Equality (ICGE) held on 12th November, 2015 at Kovalam. We have to our credit several social indices above other Indian States and on a par with developed Countries. Transgender Policy adds another feather to this tradition. The Supreme Court of India is its Judgement on 15th April, 2015 has firmly established the right to equality and equal protection for transgender persons by prohibiting discrimination on the ground of gender identity.

Govt. of Kerala was quick to act as per Supreme Court Judgement and the Social Justice Department organized a quick study. The study revealed that the transgender people face injustice at every turn: in their families and homes, in school systems that promise to shelter and educate, in harsh and exclusionary workplaces, at the markets and shops, the hotel front desk, emergency rooms and at the hands of landlords, police officers, healthcare workers and other service providers. The survey estimates presence of more than 25,000 transgenders in Kerala.

The main findings are that they face severe harassment making studies impossible, gender related negative experiences at School, lack of quota, negative

home environment, unequal treatment in hospitals, denial of jobs, meagre income. The transgenders also face denial of dignity and freedom from violence as 52% has experienced police harassment, experience of 89% mistreated at work place, sexual harassment of 28%, inability to register gender identity even at home.

The problems of the transgenders are due to the stigma and discrimination they face in the Society. The unique needs of the transgenders are overlooked and ignored by the Society. The injustice forced them to live as second class citizens. The Transgender Policy of Kerala ensures the constitutional rights of transgenders. This covers all categories of transgenders including male to female, female

policy

to male and intersex people.

The goals and objectives of Transgender Policy are all human beings have equal rights for opportunities, resources, benefits, to live with dignity, enjoy a violence free life, expression, voice, participation etc.

A Transgender Justice Board with district level Transgender Committees will be constituted to ensure the policy and the progress will be reviewed by the Social Justice Department. It is to be noted that for the first time they could exercise their franchise in the recent LSG elections by denoting their gender as transgender. The

The goals and objectives of Transgender Policy are all human beings have equal rights for opportunities, resources, benefits, to live with dignity, enjoy a violence free life, expression, voice, participation etc.

Genderpark will soon introduce T-Taxis owned and operated by transgenders in Thiruvananthapuram. Provision of their employment in Institutions will also be discussed.

A considerate approach and massive awareness of the public and employees and law enforcing agencies are required to bring the transgenders in the mainstream of social life. The Government is for that.

Getting to the Zero Zone

Zero new infection, Zero discrimination and Zero AIDS related death.

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) attacks the natural defense system of body, and can lead to Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS). Without the defense system, the body is not able to fight against the disease. Unlike some other viruses, the human body cannot get rid of HIV. That means HIV cannot be cured completely. Meanwhile, with proper medical care, HIV can be controlled. Treatment for HIV is often called Anti Retroviral Therapy or ART. It can prolong the lives of people infected with HIV and lower their chance of infecting others. Before the introduction of ART in the mid-1990s, people with HIV would progress to AIDS in just a few years. Today, someone diagnosed with HIV and get treated before the disease is far advanced can have a nearly normal life expectancy. Now, HIV infection is considered as a chronic manageable infection. HIV mainly transmits via bodily fluids such as blood,

World AIDS Day has taken place on 1 December every year since 1988. It provides an opportunity to draw attention to the HIV epidemic around the world. People organize various programs on 1 December to raise awareness of HIV and to show solidarity with people living with HIV. For many

vaginal fluid, human milk, and semen. Exchange of used needles by intravenous drug users, blood transfusions and unsafe sex are also modes of transmission of HIV/AIDS. HIV can also be transmitted from an HIV infected mother to her newborn, through child birth and breast milk. Mother-to-child transmission is the most common way that children become infected with HIV. ART medicines, given to HIV-infected women during pregnancy and childbirth and to their babies after birth, reduce the risk of mother-to-child transmission of HIV. Initially, blood transfusions were measured as the prominent source of transmission; however, currently transmission of HIV/AIDS by blood transfusion is infrequent since the donors are screened for HIV.

Diagnosis of HIV infection

Blood test is the only way to confirm the HIV status. One cannot rely on symptoms to know whether he/she is infected with HIV. Many people who are infected with HIV do not have any symptoms at all for 10 years or more. Free and confidential testing and counseling facilities are available at all Govt. Medical colleges, District hospitals, General hospitals, Taluk hospitals and selected community health centers in Kerala. It is also functioning in Thiruvananthapuram Central Railway station, and in all major prisons.

Importance of Anti Retroviral Therapy (ART)

It is important that people get tested for HIV and know that they are infected early so that medical care and treatment have the greatest effect. In Kerala, 10 ART centres and they are functioning at all 5 Govt. Medical colleges, District hospitals at Kollam, Palakkad and Kannur and

at general hospitals in Ernakulam and at Kasaragod. Through these centres, ART, CD4 testing and treatment for opportunistic infections are given to the people living with HIV (PLHIV), free of cost.

Special initiatives by Government of Kerala

- Orders issued to include all People Living with HIV (PLHIV) families in BPL list.
- Local Self Government Department approved the HIV Policy and guidelines. The HIV policy gives authority to the Panchayat Raj institutions and urban bodies to implement HIV prevention, care and support schemes.
- Financial assistance to all people living with HIV (PLHIV) and the spouses of deceased AIDS patients @ Rs.1000 per month.
- Free Diagnosis and Treatment for PLHIVs for opportunistic infections at all govt. facilities. Orders also issued to conduct pap smear test to all PLHIVs free of cost at all Govt. hospitals
- Inclusion of all students on ART in the 'Snehapooravam scheme' (a scheme for educational support to orphans) implementing by Kerala Social Security Mission.
- Treatment Care Team Supported by Kerala Social Security Mission. This scheme provides need based bystander support to inpatient PLHIVs.
- Single window system at ART Centers with the support of Kerala Social Security Mission to coordinate the social protection schemes for PLHIVs.
- Food and Nutrition support to PLHIVs by all District Panchayats ■

The writer is Project Director, Kerala State AIDS Control Society

Key Points

HIV is the virus that causes HIV infection. AIDS is the most advanced stage of HIV infection.

HIV is spread through contact with the blood, semen, pre-seminal fluid, rectal fluids, vaginal fluids, or breast milk of a person infected with HIV.

The use of HIV medicines to treat HIV infection is called Anti Retroviral Therapy (ART). ART involves taking a combination of HIV medicines every day.

ART can't cure HIV infection, but it can help people infected with HIV live longer, healthier lives. HIV medicines can also reduce the risk of transmission of HIV.

HIV cannot survive for very long time outside of the body

HIV cannot be transmitted through routine daily activities such as using a toilet seat, sharing food utensils or drinking glasses, shaking hands, or through kissing.

The virus can only be transmitted from person to person, not through animals or insect bites.

HIV transmission is possible at any stage of HIV infection— even if an HIV-infected person has no symptoms.

people the day is associated with the red ribbon, an instantly recognizable symbol. Wearing a red ribbon is a simple way to show our support. This year also the theme of World AIDS Day is 'Getting to Zero: Zero new infection, Zero discrimination and Zero AIDS related death'. In order to achieve this, a concerted collaborative effort from all sectors of the society is highly required.

Bringing the Past, the Present and the

By **Rajesh .C** in conversation with **Shaji N Karun**, Festival Advisory Committee Chairman, IFFK

Once again the movie beholders in Kerala are in the seventh heaven of happiness! Their year long waiting has come to an end. The 20th IFFK is at the threshold. And, Trivandrum is getting to be the cynosure from December 4th to 11 Dec. The festival aims at providing a common platform for the cinemas of the world to project the excellence of the film art; contributing to the

understanding and appreciation of film cultures of different nations in the context of their social and cultural ethos; and promoting friendship and cooperation among people of the world.

Kerala State Chalachitra Academy, a Kerala Government Institution to promote cinema conducts International Film Festival of Kerala (IFFK) every year. A competition section for the films from Asian and African and Latin American countries is the highlight of the festival. The Golden Crow Pheasant Award with a cash prize INR 15 lathes (approximate 30,000 US dollars) for the best feature film to be shared equally between the director and the producer

The IFFk opened a window to the world cinema and the life

portrayed in these helped us understand the cultural, political and personal lives of human lives in different countries. And, it is clearly understood that irrespective of borders, languages, cast, creed the daily life and feelings of the human race is nothing different but indisputably the same. Thus, the festival underscores a political tone and unites the people in a single thread.

In Trivandrum, about 30 years ago World cinema meant only the Hollywood ones. The yester generation can never forget Sree Kumar and Sree Visakh theatres which were built exclusively for English films. And, the advent of IFFK proved that there are cinemas worth watching and far better than those from the Hollywood.

The IFFk opened a window to the world cinema and the life portrayed in these helped us understand the cultural, political and personal lives of human lives in different countries.

future on Screen

Hence we came to know that there is a Kurosawa from Japan, A Godard from France, a Roberto Benigni from Italy and much more. We got familiar with the Children of Paradise and their Creator Majid al Majidi. Of late, a Korean with his Bohemian life style has become the icon of the IFFK. It is none other than Kim Ki Duk.

IFFK @twentieth year

The International Film Festival of Kerala enters the 20th year

this December. According to Shaji N Karun, the Festival Advisory Committee Chairman, this is a momentous moment and an opportunity to ponder about the merits and de merits IFFK has achieved since the inception of the Festival way back in 1996. The IFFK usually begins immediately after the IIFI in Goa.

INTERNATIONAL FILM
FESTIVAL OF KERALA
DEC 04-11, 2015, THIRUVANANTHAPURAM

Organized by Kerala State Chalachitra Academy, Department of Culture Affairs, Government of Kerala

The advantage Goa has over Kerala is the number of days of screening. IFFI lasts for 10 days whereas in Kerala it is reduced to one week. Hence, the number of films showing in Goa is far more than that of in Kerala." But, by 2020, the IIFK will have been competent enough to shoulder with any major festivals across the globe" Shaji says." For our dream is making IFFK as the first festival for great films to be screened for the first time. The present schedule of IFFK is one of the hindrances. By December, almost all films have been shown in major festivals, including Goa. So, when it comes to IFFK, they have lost their sheen. This problem will be solved in the short run", the Festival Advisory Committee Chairman is confident.

Shaji is all against calling the new trend in Malayalam movies, "the new generation". "This is a strange thing happening in Kerala only. No other part of the world has seen such a phenomenon. It has nothing to do

with the French New wave. And, the strangest thing is that if one film is a box office hit, the crew behind the film do not assemble together for a second one. This is not good. Film making is a team work. If one film is successful, the society expects another movie from the same team. But unfortunately, it is not happening. There were great teams in the past," Shaji reminisces.

This time 14 films, mostly from Latin America, Asia and Africa, are in the race for the Suvarna Chakoram. Bopem (Kazakhstan), Clarisse or Something About Us (Brazil), Entanglement (Turkey), Immortal (Iran) Jalal's Story (Bangladesh), Murder in Pacot (France), No woman's Land (India), Shadow Behind the Moon (Philippines), The Black Hen (Nepal), The Painted House (India), The Trap (India), The Violin Player (India) Yona (Israel), Project of the Century (Cuba) are these. There are two films, Ottal by Jayaraj and Chayam Poosiya Veedu represent

Malayalam. Jayaraj has beautifully adapted the short story of Anton Chekhov and it will be a sure bet in the competition.

The Black Hen from Nepal is woven around the ceasefire declared in 2001. Parellel to this, the social inequality and discrimination is enquired about. Draught is terrible and its terrible effect on human mind is portrayed in the film Bopem. The film from Cuba, Project of the century revolves round the economic and social problems of the country.

World Film Category

Ninety films will be screened from World Film Category.

Country Focus

Adding more sheen to the festival is the screening of films from Lithuania and Myanmar. They are included in the Country Focus category. Films from these very small countries will definitely conquer the cinematic mind of the Keralite. From Lithuania we can see Collectress,

Excursionist, Feelings, Gambler, The beauty. From Myanmar, Red Cotton Silk Flower, Successor of the merit will be screened.

Gypsy Films

Another ingredient that seasons IFFK 2015 is the Gypsy Films that are musical in nature. They are included in the Retrospective section.

Oscar Nominated Films

From 96 films nominated for Oscar, five are selected to be screened, mostly from third world countries.

Indian Cinema Now

There are seven films in Indian Cinema Now section. These are Capital 1 (Odia), Cinema Wallah (Bengali), Crime Is Punishment (Tamil), I am Not He But She (Kannada), Like a Play (Bengali), Opaala... The Journey of a Woman (Bengali), Song of the Horned Owl (Assamese).

Most of these films deal with women's issues.

Malayalam Cinema Today

Seven Malayalam Films are included Malayalam Cinema Today Category. Ozhivu Divasathe Kali (Sanal Kumar Sashidharan), Valiya Chirakulla Pakshikal (Dr. Bijukumar Damodaran), Nirnaayakam V.K Prakash), Pathemari (Salim Ahamed), Ain (Siddhartha Siva), Kaattum Mazhayum (R. Harikumar), Munroe Thuruthu (Manu P.S).

Restored Indian Classics

Old, Indian classic films are included in this category.

Lifetime achievement Award

Eminent filmmaker and spearhead of Iran's cinematic renaissance Dariush Mehrjui is bestowed with the lifetime achievement award of this year's IFFK. At the vanguard of the Iranian New Wave movement of the 1970, Mehrjui introduced hitherto little-explored cinematic themes and narratives. Infused with a heady mix of realism and symbolism, his

films helped foster the development of art house sensibilities among a fast-maturing cinema audience. After debuting with the unsuccessful Diamond 33 (1966), a big budget parody of Bond films, Mehrjui found acclaim and recognition with Gaav (The Cow, 1969), the film was adapted from a short story by Iranian literary giant Gholamhossein Sa'edi.

His films find kinship with the works of Roberto Rossellini, Vittorio de Sica and Satyajit Ray, his oeuvre possess a distinctively Iranian flavour in part because they were mostly inspired from Iranian literature. In 1973, Mehrjui created his magnum opus; The Cycle (1975). It was Iran's first submission for Best Foreign Language Film at the 50th Academy Awards in 1977. The film was banned for three years before being released in Iran in 1978. Mehrjui will be feted at the IFFK 2015 inaugural ceremony. A cash prize of Rs 5 lakh accompanies the citation. ■

The writer is Asst. Editor I&PRD

Brief Encounter

The Best Romantic Film of All Time

There'll come a time in the future when I shan't mind about this anymore, when I can look back and say quite peacefully and cheerfully how silly I was. No, no, I don't want that time to come ever. I want to remember every minute, always, always to the end of my days.-Laura Jesson in Brief Encounter

David Lean, widely known for his epics such as *Lawrence of Arabia*, *A Passage to India*, and *The Bridge on the River Kwai* made only one romantic film in his entire career. Till date, hardly any movies of the genre compete with this one and half hour romantic tear jerker. Brilliantly crafted and judiciously cast, it has stood against the tides of time since its coming out in 1946. With a very downbeat ending, Lean's film is a simple but realistically-honest, self-told social melodrama of the quiet desperation involved in an extra-marital love affair between two married, middle-class individuals over seven weekly meetings, mostly against the backdrop of a railway station.

The year 2016 will see the 70th anniversary of *Brief encounter* and many cinemas in England is ready to screen it for the new generation. For the self styled intelligetia, *Brief Encounter* does not satisfy their aesthetic sense as it is a fashion for them to mock at romance let alone Shakespearean Romantic comedies. But, for the honest, devoid of jaundiced eye, this small film is a timeless one. It is usually said that one of the touchstones of deciding whether a work of art is a classic or not is the urge for reading it or seeing it again and again. If this be the criterion, then this must be a classic

as *Romeo and Juliet* in reading.

Love can be expressed in many ways. In Shakespearean plays, love happens at first sight. And, the moment one falls in love is a momentous one. In *brief encounter*, it is beautifully taken that the beholder will carry the moment throughout his life. The film starts with the anti climax from which is the climax of the film. Most of the scenes are shot in a railway station and in trains. The protagonist Alec Harvey (Trevor Howard) and the heroine Laura Jesson (Celia Johnson) are not much impressive in their physical features but with the directorial sharpness David lean bypasses all other minor flaws.

The fate of the love affair between Alec and Laura is decided from the very beginning itself. Both are married and leading undisturbed family lives.

Laura at one point says, "Nothing lasts, really. Neither happiness nor

despair. Not even life lasts very long."

This is true, but the film also shows how the statement is false. Paradoxically, by cutting the relationship short, the relationship, the brief encounter, lives on, albeit in a different, invisible sphere. Laura and Alec are similar to the couple in John Keats' poem "Ode on a Grecian Urn." One of

the drawings on the old urn features a man and woman, almost to embrace but forever separated by the urn.

Bold Lover, never, never canst thou kiss,

Though winning near the goal — yet, do not grieve;

She cannot fade, though thou hast not thy bliss,

For ever wilt thou love and she be fair!

Laura and Alec experienced an idyll that was never fulfilled — most idylls are cut short, sadly — which may be exactly what makes the idyll so powerful and meaningful and lasting, for better or for worse. Though it moves into the past, it stays in our minds, tantalizing us even on the dullest days.

The screenplay is by Noël Coward; based on his 1936 one-act play *Still Life* is unforgettable. Most of the dialogues and monologues in the film are still echoed in the minds of the movie goers. ■

The writer is Asst. Editor, I&PRD.

Scribbling the First Letter of Literacy

When Chellimoopathi from Kookkum Palayam ooru at Attapadi scribbles the first letter of the Malayalam alphabet, it becomes a literal start up for the enlightenment of the whole tribes in Kerala. The Kerala State Literacy

by KSLMA to bring as many tribes as possible to participate in this endeavour. Education minister P.K. Abdu Rabb inaugurated the programme by giving Chellimoopathi the piece of chalk to write the first letter of the Malayalam

- will be covered. The first phase aims at achieving total literacy, the second phase focus on implementing the Literacy mission's equivalency programmes. The services of 300 instructors from tribal areas, who have passed class X, will be used for the programme, which is being implemented by KSLMA in association with the Education Department.

A survey on continuing education in tribal areas will also be conducted in the first phase, which is expected to be completed in six months. According to a survey conducted in 2008, the literacy rate in the tribal areas of the state is 72.77 %. However, the literacy rate at Attapadi tribal area is only 67.63 %. A reason for the low literacy rate at Attapadi can be attributed to the break in literacy programmes of AGHARTS in the area date back to 2010. The approach paper of the state planning Board in the 12th Five Year Plan (2012- 17) has mentioned in detail about the need for literacy programmes in tribal areas of the State. ■

The writer is PRO, KSLMA

Mission Authority (KSLMA) launched the programme aimed at achieving total literacy in tribal areas of the state; on September 15, 2015 (It is the programme under mission 676 of the State government).

A part from academicians and representatives of Local bodies, hundreds of tribes from various oorus at Palakkad district thronged to witness the solemn function. Elaborate arrangements were made

alphabet on the slate.

In the first phase, around 5,000 beneficiaries in three Grama Panchayats of Attapadi-Agali, Puthoor and Sholayar

Treaty of immense Significance

Tashkent Treaty celebrates its golden jubilee

The Tashkent Treaty is nearing its 50th year. The Tashkent declaration of 10th January 1966 was a peace agreement between India and Pakistan after the Indo-Pakistani War of 1965. Kashmir has

always been a major bone of contention between India and Pakistan. Already four wars have been fought for this Paradise on Earth. The first was in 1947-48 the second in 1965, third in

1971 and the last one in Kargil in 1999.

Pakistan has always tried to provoke India. But India has always tried to remain tolerant even in extreme provocation. India retaliated whenever such

attacks mount from across the border.

The Tashkent Treaty was the result of a combined effort. The prominent leaders of England, the US and the erstwhile Soviet

Union had significant role in shaping it. The then Soviet President Alexei Kosygin's role was noteworthy. The treaty was signed between Indian Prime Minister Lal Bahadur Shastri and Pakistan

President Ayub Khan as per United Nations Charter. The treaty realized the ceasefire between the two nations. Following the treaty, India gave Pakistan back the land it seized from Pakistan

contingent of the Indian Army stepped on the Pakistani soil after the partition in 1947.

The British premiere Harold Wilson took initiative for a ceasefire. His efforts became fruitful in July in 1965. The two countries signed a ceasefire treaty on July 1st and the confrontations came to an end.

But Pakistan was not ready to accept the Olive Branch India extended. It operated its heinous agenda secretly. Pakistan designed another operation, Operation Grand slam (The activities done by

occupied Punjab.

The mesmerizing beauty of Kashmir ,the paradise on earth has always lured Pakistan was the reason for the war in 1965 .It is also known as the second Kashmir War. The sole aim was to create mayhem in Kashmir and make pandemonium in India. This led to the war in 1965. Around 30,000 invaders infiltrated

Pakistan in the Akhnoor Sector of Kashmir) to make Kashmir on their part. This time India decided to give a fitting reply.

The Tashkent treaty was signed at an appropriate time. The Indian army was on the verge of conquering Lahore. When the treaty was signed, the army retreated. India Defended the attack on Rajasthan but at Akhanoor sector India suffered some casualties. That was the only set back India had in this war.

India was ready to give back the weapons it seized from Pakistan. Both countries were ready to maintain the pre- war situation.

India has always been on the part of maintaining peace. Even in Kargil war, India was forced to retaliate after repeated provocations from Pakistan. India is led by the Upanishad mantra “Loka Samastah Sukhino Bhavanthu”. ■

into India through the ceasefire treaty border. They unleashed attacks and ambushes on areas like Thithwal, Uri and Poonch. India retaliated strongly on attacking the northern Pakistan by crossing the International border in Lahore.

But every war finally results in the loss of lives. Thousands lost their lives on both sides. It was a big war on the land, on sea and in sky. Canons were used extensively. It was the second time cannons were used for such an extent. The first time they were used extensively was in the Second World War. The biggest

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over the past four years has been running in profit. Its business has been diversified and it has started a chain of production and sales units for top notch and delicious bakery products that live up to the KTDC brand name. More than 50 tourism initiatives of KTDC at various stages of implementation are in progress.

In recognition of the primacy of classical art in tourism, the state government has instituted the Nishagandhi award in association with the annual Nishagandhi fest as the state level award for classical dance and music. The award has been instituted in such a way that the felicitation comprising prize money of 1lakh, memento and certificate can be awarded alternately for classical dance and music each year. The debut awardee was veteran classical dancer Mrinalini Sarabhai.

The state has also articulated projects for the expansion of Malabar tourism. The execution of the master plan for expansion of Bekkal Tourist Center has commenced and the construction of Thalassery Tourism Project is progressing.

Eco Tourism and Adventure Tourism are new and promising areas for Kerala tourism. The government is envisioning novel projects in these hitherto unexplored sectors. An Adventure Tourism Promotion Society has been formed in order to integrate the efforts for expansion of Adventure Tourism in the state. The Society has been organizing exciting mountain cycling competitions at the international level for past three years to further the promotion of Adventure Tourism. It has also spearheaded paragliding competitions at Wagamon. Plans have been put in place to expand Eco Tourism into fresh arenas.

I am extremely delighted at the fact that state tourism ventures

into its new projects for this year by commencing the implementation of the “God’s Own Country; People’s Own Tourism” and “Hop On-Hop Off and Water Taxi boat service” projects which were charted out last year.

Adopting the right background measures for effective and optimal utilization of state’s resources is the prime role of

government as far as tourism is concerned. The current government’s approach towards tourism sector is in complete acknowledgement of its substantial role in state’s development. Only a modicum of Kerala’s tourism assets has been exploited progressively. Aqua tourism, hilltop-echo-adventure tourism, heritage tourism, health (Ayurvedic) tourism, cultural tourism, beach tourism and shopping tourism are highly promising areas in tourism that have not been explored to their fullest potential. Productive utilization of opportunities in these sectors would speed up the overall development of our state, with tourism turning into the backbone of its economy.

But the expansion of background measures for effective resource utilization should not be confined within the government sector alone.

Our tourism projects must be time bound and competitive. An inept approach could easily cost us a handful of golden opportunities. The situation also calls for the participation of

private investors for the state to benefit from its real potential. The government has thus formulated a new tourism policy that includes equally fervent schemes for the development of the public as well as private sectors. It must not however be forgotten that tourism has not yet been successful in claiming due priority in the State’s development plans in accordance with the crucial role this sector plays in Kerala’s progress.

There should be obligatory and purposeful intervention of government in the preservation of our environment. Government has strongly intervened in issues such as deforestation and conservation of river banks by preventing indiscriminate sand hauling. The present directive is to make such involvements on the part of the government widespread and more pronounced. This is essential for a prosperous tourism industry to thrive and also to ensure that our Kerala continues to be the archive of rarities so graphically captured in McKibben’s words. ■

UN and India

Hand in hand for a better tomorrow

On 24th October 2015 the United Nations completed its very eventful 70 years and three months before our nation celebrated 68th year of Independence. The birthdays of the two superpowers indicate that both UN and India had grown just about the same phase.

The UN and India has had good diplomatic relations. The international organisation which came into being after the World War 1, was christened as "United Nations" by the American President Franklin Roosevelt.

With the passage of time, new members got enrolled and the UN became a powerful organisation.

Indian Personalities

India has strongly backed UN principles and objectives and made valuable contribution to the Charter. Rajkumari Amrit Kaur who was the first president of WHO, Najma Heptulla, Justice P.N. Bhagawati and Shashi Tharoor are among the distinguished Indians who donned a various important roles in the UN.

The Indian personalities who have made it to UN in the most unique and conspicuous way are dime a dozen and for sure they are the epoch-makers - be it V.K. Krishna Menon, who delivered

a continuous and contented 8-hour long speech in the general assembly or M.S. Subhalakshmi who was the first person ever to enthral the UN with her iconic and legendary music. This list has more Indian names like former Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee and Mata Amritananda Mayi who delivered speeches in Hindi and Malayalam respectively.

Jawaharlal Nehru's speech in New York in 1956 where he said - "Even if the

United Nations did not do anything wonderful, the mere fact of UN has been of great significance to the world."

The services of Vijay Lakshmi Pandit as President of the UN General Assembly, are always remembered fondly. India has played many significant roles for a better world. It was the co-sponsor of the landmark 1960 Declaration in UN for granting of Independence to Colonial Countries. India spoke against apartheid and racial

discrimination in South Africa.

India's status as a founding member of the Non-Aligned Movement and the Group of 77 cemented its position within the UN.

India has been advocating "Zero tolerance" approach to terrorism in all its forms. It has taken part in 43 peacekeeping operations, contributing 1,60,000 troops

India remains the only State possessing nuclear weapons to call unambiguously for a Nuclear Weapons Convention to ban and eliminate nuclear weapons. The contribution, rich cultural heritage and traditions of the country have been recognised duly in UN. On 11 December 2014, the UNGA adopted without a vote, a resolution commemorating 21 June as the International Yoga

Day.

India has invested a lot in UN and it believes strongly in the norms and objectives laid down by the organisation.

As one of the greatest sons of India, A.P.J Abdul Kalam put it ;"We have guided machines but misguided human beings" and UN being the right core to guide the human resource of the world in the right path let "US" --both India and UN cooperate together, as we did all these years for a better tomorrow. ■